

IMPACT OF INVESTMENT FOR REGIONAL AND LOCAL DEVELOPMENT

Egamberganov Jakhongir Jabbargan o'gli

Student of Economics faculty, Urgench State University,

Khorezm, Uzbekistan

E-mail address: economist.jahongir@gmail.com

Abstract

In the recent era, we focus on the investment outcomes and their impact over the primary health care sector of China. as, the world health organization announced its vision in the very early days of its origination that the primary health to all at an equal basis is the basic right of the human being as a part of a state. To evaluate the methodology of the phenomenon, we selected various districts of China from different regions. From the east, Shandong and Liaoning and from the central region Hubei and Shanxi. Shanxi and Sichuan from the west. The included CHSC were 7 and THs were around 17. The financing was released to those 34 CHSCs and 92 THs. When any government tends to facilitate the people and introduces some long term policies for the growth and development of the country, the investment at the local as well as at the international level ensure the conformity of the local sectors to sustain and to contain a reliable sources for the up gradation of the lives of the people.as, the health care policy of the China is concerned, it's very eminent that is a is a significant drift in the graph of the revenue from the health sector of China

Introduction

Government policies are ever focused on the upgradation and improvement in the public sectors to provide the maximum possible facilities to the people of that country. For this purpose, the most fundamental tool, used is the investment in various sectors of the country. investments at the local and regional grounds promotes and boost the economy of the country to stand enough to provide solid grounds for the implementation of the government policies for the welfare and improvement in the life

standards of the people. After a profitable and fruitful investment approaches, the governments, then decide to priorities the fundamental public sectors to be improved on the immediate grounds. In the recent era, we focus on the investment outcomes and their impact over the primary health care sector of China. as, the world health organization announced its vision in the very early days of its origination that the primary health to all at an equal basis is the basic right of the human being as a part of a state. Keeping in view, China has introduced a three years program to approach to the poor and affording classes of the society, even in the rural and urban areas as well to provide them quality health services at their ease (A Pike, 2016). In the recent data, collected about the china’s investment in the primary health care system is a considerable chunk of national economy (Pavlínek, 2004).The major achievement of the country, in this regard is the considerable number of health insurance of the people which has yielded a balance of input vs output of the investment.

Methodology

We employed stratified sampling for this study. We chose six provinces based on location and on the level of economic development. These provinces were Shandong and Liaoning province in the eastern region, Hubei and Shanxi province in the central region, as well as Shaanxi Zhang et al. BMC Health Services. To evaluate the methodology of the phenomenon, we selected various districts of China from different regions. From the east, Shandong and Liaoning and from the central region Hubei and Shanxi. Shanxi and Sichuan from the west. The included CHSC were 7 and THs were around 17. The financing was released to those 34 CHSCs and 92 THs. The comparison was made among the government financing allocation, revenue generated and the number of people engaged in this regard. The time period is considered from January 2010 to September 2010. Then it’s evaluated between jan.2011 to September 2011.

Province	2011			2010		
	Mean	Minimum	Maximum	Median	Minimum	Maximum
Hubei	1717	130	7830	1244	30	5160
Liaoning	1139	50	6400	613	0	4139
Shandong	1806	410	5290	852	0	3380
Shanxi	549	30	2740	409	20	1920
Shaanxi	1225	90	2750	1102	100	2372
Sichuan	1239	0	13080	1034	37	12715
Average	1300	0	13080	881	0	12715

It was indicated by the calculation that government was lenient to invest more to achieve the desired goals of financial inputs.

If we assume this as indicator “A”

Government financing proportion = financial revenue from government/total revenue from primary health care institutions

Then the second indicator is assumed as “B” =financial revenue from government/ people for the provided facilities.

Province	A2008	A2009	A2010	A2011	A2011 – A2010	P values
Hubei	—	—	33.27	43.23	9.96	0.024
Liaoning	—	—	27.19	40.32	13.13	0.001
Shandong	—	—	19.36	35.36	16.00	0.000
Shanxi	—	—	34.00	35.23	1.23	0.269
Shaanxi	—	—	48.80	53.40	4.60	0.218
Sichuan	—	—	29.50	32.15	2.65	0.262
Average	18.2	19.3	29.86	38.84	8.98	0.000
P values	—	—	0.000	0.074	—	—

Discussion

When any government tends to facilitate the people and introduces some long term policies for the growth and development of the country, the investment at the local as well as at the international level ensure the conformity of the local sectors to sustain and to contain a reliable sources for the up gradation of the lives of the people.as, the health care policy of the China is concerned, it’s very eminent that is a is a significant drift in the graph of the revenue from the health sector of China (Yi, 2021).More people are insured, the more revenue is collected to support the economy of the country. It’s evident from the statistical data, from the economical surveys and statistics that China

invests US\$ 124 billion in 2009 to 2011 and then \$206 billion invested in 2015. It is revealed that 44% funds were allocated from the primary health care system (yeng.lee, 2020). Through these programs, Chinese government succeeded to run the primary health care system at a very smooth grounds in which the people at the grass level are highly satisfied with quality and standards of the health care provided to them (Tan, 2022). Another relevant achievement of the government is to support the drugs supplying companies with the revenues from health care sector on the profit free grounds.

Conclusion

As, if we consider the government financial institution of as an entity “A” and the primary health care sector as an entity “B” then we, through calculations find that the investment through government results in the outcome and revenue generation from the health care sector. After a series of evolutionary sequences, China is at the crux of the development in establishing the primary health care system of the country. Since, 2009, consecutive programs to improve and to yield the expected outcomes, now it has been determined by the statistical and intelligentsia of the country, to establish a firm and solid frame work and to establish the health care system as an institution. As, the calculations and estimations reveal that the investment through government financial institution.

References

1. A Pike, A. R.-P. (2016). Local and regional development. local and regional development .
2. Pavlínek, P. (2004). Regional development implications of foreign direct investment in Central Europe. regional ... investment.
3. Tan, L. Y. (2022). Equality in China’s healthcare infrastructure.
4. Wan, G. (2021). The trend in primary health care preference in China: a cohort study of 12,508 residents from 2012 to 2018. BMC Health Services Research.yeng.lee. (2020). HOW DOES CHINA’S HEALTHCARE SYSTEM ACTUALLY WORK?
5. Yi, B. (2021). An overview of the Chinese healthcare system. An overview of the Chinese healthcare system.